

In Vitro Antimicrobial Effects of Stem Bark Extracts of *Vernonia Amygdalina*

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Received: May 9, 2014, Accepted: May 29, 2014, Published: May 3, 2014.

ABSTRACT

An in vitro evaluations were carried out on dried stem bark of *Vernonia amygdalina* by examining the inhibitory potentials of methanolic and chloroform (methyl trichloride or formyl trichloride) extracts of the plant on some selected gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria, the effects and activities were compared with the activities of some selected standard drugs on cultured medium of these bacteria which are potential causative agents of various public and easily communicable and non-communicable infections. The diameter (mm) of zone of inhibition of the extracts using 200mg/ml was determined on cultured media on four bacterial pathogens.

Keyword: in vitro, *Vernonia amygdalina*, pathogens, antibiotics.

INTRODUCTION

The plant *Vernonia amygdalina* (biter leave) is a compositae that has its origin from Nigeria [1]. It is usually called biter leave due to its taste and it's used in traditional medicine as tonic and remedy against different and diverse illnesses and various infectious diseases [2]. It has found relevance in traditional folk's medicine as anthelmint and serves one of the major commonly expressed plants both locally and in most urban areas to safe human from the ordeals of bacterial activities. Infectious diseases account for one half of all deaths in the tropical countries irrespective of efforts made in controlling the incidence of epidemic [3, 4].

The leaves of the plant are of importance use economically, it is used instead of Hops in beer production. Several Stigmastane-type saponins such as vernoniosides A1, B1, A2, and A3etc have been identified in the leave. The antioxidant activities of luteolin, β -glucoside flavonoid compounds isolated from the leaves of *V. amygdalina* have been reported using coupled oxidation of β -carotene linoleic acid [5]. It is to be noted as well that the nutritional and the antioxidant supplements which can defile the potency of some pathogenic bacteria come from plant sources. These plants often exhibit a wide collection of biological and pharmacological activities, as well as anti-inflammatory, anti-fungal and anti-bacterial properties [6, 9]. The macerated leaves parts of the plant are used in making soup while the water extract serves as tonic drink for the prevention of certain illness. *V. amygdalina* has been reported for its use by wild animals. The leave also has found relevance in traditional folk medicine as

anti-helminthic, a laxative herb and ant-malaria as it has been reported to have treated parasite- related diseases in Tanzania [7].

MATERIALS USED AND METHODS

The bark of the plant used were plant collected from Federal University of Technology, Akure in Ondo State, Nigeria, identified by a taxonomist with a herbarium number BOT/NAU/1314.

The method used here for the extractions was that described by [8].

Sample Preparation

The samples were air dried for few days and powdered using a Philips blender. The powder kept in a clean container at $\pm 37^{\circ}\text{C}$ for further extractions. The infusion of each of the extracts was screened for the phytochemical components.

Extraction from blended samples

100g of the washed powder was soaked in 500ml of the extraction solvent (methanol and chloroform) separately for 72 hours with occasional shaking. The extracts were evaporated at room temperature to obtain concentrated extracts. The air- dried extracts were stored at room temperature for further studies. The percentage yield was also obtained which was then calculated as followed;

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{\text{Extract obtained in mg}}{\text{Crude plant sample in mg}} \times 100$$

Method used for Antimicrobial screening of the extract

The Chloroform and methanolic extracts of the bark of *V. amygdalina* were each screened *in vitro* for antimicrobial activity against the selected pathogenic micro-organisms using the method described by [10]. A loop-full of the pure culture of each of the test organisms obtained from the Microbiology Department of the Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA) was subcultured on nutrient broth medium. The nutrient broth medium was prepared with 1.5g of the nutrient broth in 100ml distilled water. This was well stirred until the nutrient broth medium was poured into MacConkey bottles. The bottles were tightly closed and autoclaved at 115°c and the inoculating loop was heated with a spirit lamp and then used for the inoculation process. Briefly after this, the introduction of 200mg/ml (20% dilution) extract into a made hole at the centre of the plate was then followed after which the inoculation with the pathogenic organism was then followed and tightly packed and incubated at 25°c for 48hours (2 days). After incubation, the inoculated plates were observed for zone inhibition (diameter in mm).

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

The sensitivity or Susceptibility of the test micro-organism to standard drug was tested using inoculated agar plate and streptomycin. The zone of inhibition were measured and compared with those of the plant extracts. This was used as positive test control. Sterile water was used as negative control which did not show any effect on the test organisms.

DISCUSSION

The quantitative confirmation of phytochemical constituents of this plant has been extensively studied on the stem bark of *vernonia amygdalina*; it suggests that the plant bark is rich in considerable amount of these phytochemicals which can be fundamental basis for proffering treatments for most bacterial triggering infections and diseases. Considering table 1 above, the methanolic extracts of the plant inhibits the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* significantly ($p > 0.05$) with the value 9.0 ± 0.4 and chloroform extract 8.0 ± 0.1 , while *Bacillus aureus* was inhibited with diameter of inhibition of 8.0 ± 0.1 with both extracts but with significant ($p < 0.05$) different in diameter of inhibition with the extracts in *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi*. This suggests that the extracts have inhibitory potentials against these pathogenic bacteria when the effects were contrasted with the values achieved from standard antibiotics in the table 2 above.

Bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* has been reported to be the cause of 80–85% of urinary tract infections [11]. Waterborne diseases are the leading cause of deaths globally, estimated to result in more than 3.4 million deaths and approximately 4 billion circumstances of diarrhea annually according to the World Health Organization (WHO) [12]. In unusual cases, viral or fungal infections cause urinary tract infections which can serve a resilient relief from manacles of preventable deadly diseases. More also, these phytochemicals can serve crucial purposes in enabling man from activities of microbes by meddling with the cell division and the movements performed by microfilaments.

Table 1. The results below are the diameters of zone of inhibition (mm) observed from antibiotic activities of two different extracts of the stem bark of *vernonia amygdalina* with 200mg/ml of the extracts on some selected disease causing pathogens. From the table 200mg/ml of both extracts has highest inhibition on *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus aureus* respectively.

Pathogens	Diameters of zone	Chloroform
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	of inhibition(mm) Methanolic Extract	Extract
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7.0 ± 0.5	8.0 ± 0.1
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	9.0 ± 0.4	8.0 ± 0.1
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	8.0 ± 0.2	7.0 ± 0.5
<i>Bacillus aureus</i>	8.0 ± 0.1	8.0 ± 0.1

Table 2. Antibiotic disc sensitivity zone of inhibition for some of the selected standard antibiotics (in µmg) on two selected pathogens. Erythromycin, ofloxacin and amoxicillin prevented considerable level of growth of these pathogenic agents.

Antibiotics	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Clotrimazole	-	-
Amoxicillin	++	+
Cephalexin		
Clexaxillin	-	+
Erythromycin	-	++
Ofloxacin	++	++
	++	++

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Citation: Afolabi Olakunle B. , et al (2014). In Vitro Antimicrobial Effects of Stem Bark Extracts of Vernonia Amygdalina. *J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences*. VII3. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.VII3.03

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